

Supplementary Table S1. Specimens and GenBank accession numbers of DNA sequences used in the phylogenetic analysis. All sequences of *R. ayubiana* were produced in this study.

<i>Taxon</i>	<i>Voucher collection (herbarium)</i>	<i>Country</i>	<i>mtSSU</i>	<i>LSU</i>	<i>RPB2</i>	<i>TEF1α</i>
<i>R. adulterina</i>	SAV F-4451	Poland	MG386730		MG386750	
<i>R. abbotabadensis</i>	LAH 310099	Pakistan	MG386718		MG386736	
<i>R. abbotabadensis</i>	LAH 310071	Pakistan	MG386719	MN518356	MG386737	MZ364137
<i>R. abbotabadensis</i>	FH 00304558	Pakistan	MG386721	MN518355	MG386738	MZ364138
<i>R. ayubiana</i>	LAH 35438	Pakistan	MZ364121	MZ358816	MZ364131	MZ364139
<i>R. ayubiana</i>	LAH 35439	Pakistan	MZ364122	MZ358817	MZ364132	MZ364140
<i>R. cuprea</i>	GENT (2010 BT168)	Germany	MG386731	MZ358818	MG386751	
<i>R. dryadicola</i>	TURA 151632	Finland	MG386728	MN518357	MG386745	MZ364141
<i>R. dryadicola</i>	TURA 152390	Finland	MG386729	MZ358820	MG386746	MZ364142
<i>R. dryadicola</i>	UPS (at2004140)	Sweden	MZ364125	MN518358	MG386747	MZ364143
<i>R. dryadicola</i>	IB 2002/0432	Italy	MG386722	MZ358819	MG386739	
<i>R. globispora</i>	SAV (HK12021)	Sweden	MZ364123	MN518362	MZ364133	MZ364144
<i>R. globispora</i>	GENT (2007 BT121)	Germany	MG386726	MG944274	MG386743	MZ364145
<i>R. globispora</i>	GENT (2007 BT98)	Germany	MG386727	MZ358822	MG386744	MZ364146
<i>R. globispora</i>	GENT (2010 BT188)	Germany	MZ364124	MZ358821	MZ364134	MZ364147
<i>R. juniperina</i>	SAV F-4998	Italy			MG386749	MZ364148
<i>R. maculata</i>	SAV F-2130	Estonia	MG944263	MG944277	MG944253	
<i>R. maculata</i>	SAV F-933	Slovakia	MG944262	MG944275	MZ364135	
<i>R. mansehraensis</i>	HUP SUR 180	Pakistan	MG944266	MG944280	MG944255	
<i>R. mansehraensis</i>	HUP SUR 803	Pakistan	MG944267		MG944256	
<i>R. mattirolaana</i>	KRA F-2018-1	Poland	MZ364126	MK105723	MZ364136	MZ364149
<i>R. mattirolaana</i>	KRA F-2018-2	Poland	MZ364127	MK105724	MK102759	MZ364150
<i>R. mattirolaana</i>	GK8136	Greece		MK105722	MK102758	
<i>R. mediterraneensis</i>	MCVE 29086 (MG636)	Italy	MZ364128	MZ358824	MK102761	MZ364151
<i>R. mediterraneensis</i>	MCVE 29085 (MG630)	Italy	MZ364129	MZ358823	MK102760	
<i>R. nymphaeum</i>	M (HM R-12180)	France	MG944270	MG944283	MG944259	
<i>R. nymphaeum</i>	STU (HJB10019)	Belgium	MZ364130	MN518353	DQ421956	
<i>R. quercus-floribundae</i>	LAH 36219	Pakistan	MN053397	MN513043	MN053389	MZ364152

<i>R. quercus-floribundae</i>	LAH 36220	Pakistan	MN053396	MN513043	MN053390	MZ364153
<i>R. tengii</i>	HMAS 264837	China	MG386733	MN518360	MG386753	MG386707
<i>R. tengii</i>	HMAS 262728	China	MG386734		MG386754	MZ364154
<i>R. tengii</i>	HMAS 244255	China	MG386735		MG386755	MZ364155
<i>R. tengii</i>	HMAS 251829	China	MG386732	MN518359	MG386752	MZ364156